

Manuel Graña <ccpgrrom@gmail.com>

[Diagnostics] Manuscript ID: diagnostics-2681155 - Comment - Accepted for Publication

1 message

Diagnostics Editorial Office <diagnostics@mdpi.com>

Mon, Oct 28, 2024 at 8:54 AM

Reply-To: Lynn Fu <lynn.fu@mdpi.com>, Diagnostics Editorial Office <diagnostics@mdpi.com>

To: Manuel Graña <ccpgrrom@gmail.com>

Cc: Goizalde Badiola-Zabala <goizalde.badiola@ehu.eus>, Guillermo Cano-Escalera <guillermo.cano@ehu.eus>, Diagnostics Editorial Office <diagnostics@mdpi.com>, Lynn Fu <lynn.fu@mdpi.com>

Dear Professor Graña,

We are writing to let you know that your comment has been accepted and will be published shortly.

Manuscript ID: diagnostics-2681155

Type of manuscript: Comment

Title: A critical reading of "COVID-19 Prediction Using Black-Box Based Pearson Correlation Approach"

Authors: Manuel Graña *, Goizalde Badiola-Zabala, Guillermo Cano-Escalera

Received: 9 Oct 2023

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If you have any questions please do not hesitate to contact us.

Kind regards,
Andreas Kjaer
Editor-in-Chief